

Mechanisms For Directing Volunteer Work To Curb Unhealthy Behaviors On Campus (A Proposed Perception To Activate The Role Of Volunteer Work In The Face Of Intellectual Deviation Among University Students)

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Article Info	Abstract
Article History	<i>Background: Unhealthy behavior among university students setting has been linked with obesity, low academic success, more numerous health complaints, life skills, poor self-reported health status longer time spent watching TV, regular smoking, poor emotional well-being and unhealthy eating habits and drunkenness. The massive impact of new communications technologies is another transformation that has considerable impact on how casual, post-disaster volunteering takes place, and undeniably every kind of disaster volunteering. The current study aims to identify the unhealthy behaviors among university students, and their link to the use of social media, as well as, identifying whether the digital volunteering can help mitigate unhealthy behavior or not.</i>
Received: May 28, 2021	<i>Methods: An anonymous structured questionnaire was used to gather data for the study. The data sample consists of 220 students and staff of Princess Nourah bint Abdulrahman University, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. The survey design included questions about socio-demographic characteristics, Types of violating behaviors committed by female students at the university, relationship between the use of social networks and unhealthy behaviors, Reasons behind the wrong behaviors committed by students and Powers used to deal with a student with unhealthy behavior.</i>
Accepted: October 29, 2021	<i>Results: The result revealed that smoking is the most common single type of unhealthy behavior listed by the respondents 4 (18.2%). Also all the respondents agreed that there is a relationship between the use of social media and the exhibition of unhealthy behavior by students. The most common site used by students who suffer from wrong behavior was recreational sites (40.9%), this is followed pornographic sites (22.7%); others utilize both recreation and pornographic sites (22.7%). Recreation, educational and cultural sites combined are the less likely used sites by students suffering from wrong behavior. There was a weak correlation (0.365) between factors that instigate unhealthy behavior and the detection of unhealthy behavior (and awareness of its harms). The Sig. (2 tailed) was 0.094 indicating that there is a statistically significant correlation between the two variables.</i>
Keywords : Campus, Intellectual Deviation, Unhealthy Behavior, University Students, Volunteer Work	<i>Conclusions: The results show that unhealthy behaviors exist among university students and these unhealthy behaviors are strongly linked to the use of social media. The study also reveals that digital volunteering can help to mitigate unhealthy behaviors and its effect among university students.</i>
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Introduction

There is an increasing proof of the importance of electronic technologies in promoting access to healthcare. The World Health Organization (WHO) defines digital health as “a discrete functionality of digital technology that is applied to achieve health objectives” [1]. The significance of digital health is valued in patient management, research, and support to low curb health workers, including gathering and analyzing data, disease inspection, and community health workers, along with other applications. This is principally fundamental in limited resource locations [2]. The importance of digital technologies is esteemed for its capacity to surpass environmental obstacles while permitting live access to essential health services [3, 4]. There are global, regional and national strategies and guidelines regarding employment of digital health to encourage the achievement of worldwide health coverage. The WHO lately released the first set of guiding principle [5], in this regard; pointing out that “digital health cannot substitute non-functional health systems”. Electronic health (e-health) readiness is defined as “preparedness of healthcare institutions or communities for the anticipated change brought by programs related to information and communications technology” [6]. Programs

implementation is challenging in absence of e-readiness. The present East African Community (EAC) Health Sector Investment precedence agenda (2018–2028) [7], in all the nine (9) priority areas, emphasizes the regional block's commitment to exploit the potential of e-health on the road to global health coverage. The EAC is made up of six (6) partner states: Kenya, Rwanda, Burundi, United Republic of Tanzania, Uganda and South Sudan. The EAC health administrative body, through the ministers' of health has called on countries to execute e-health approaches, with a suggestion that the East African Science and Technology Commission carry out a regional e-health readiness evaluation. In 2011 (2011–2017), Kenya launched its foremost National e-health policy [8], with a rallying cry to reinforce the health scheme and afterwards extend evenhandedness in health care to the marginalized and poor population. Five main areas were identified which include electronic health records (health information systems); m-health (mobile technologies in health); telemedicine; information for citizens; and distance education or eLearning for health professionals[9]. The National e-Health Policy (2016–2030) supervened this strategy, restating the creation of a favorable atmosphere that encourages acceptance, execution and use of e-Health at all echelons of service rendering. The e-Health policy and strategy were corroborated by the Kenya Health Policy (2014–2030) that is one of its aims is to devise and establish Information and Communication Technology framework and software for the essential healthcare management and implementation[8]. Though Kenya, and some other countries in the EAC have established their national e-health strategies, inadequate scientific facts on the profits of digital health mediations, the way they function in various circumstances inside health systems continue to be key limiting factors to facts based programming and policy.

Lately, Social media have seen a massive order and utilization by every sector and demographic strata of the society, particularly the young people of school age. These sites have become medium for conversation and instrument for opinions and ideas exchange. They also serve to gather supporters for those ideas. It therefore becomes a major device for transformation in every stage and aspect, a conduit for making choices and intellectual knowledge development in societies as a whole. Against the backdrop that youths of school age are not able to effectively make constructive judgment between falsehood and truth, and what is wrong and right due to some intellectual conflicts that have materialized like: extremism, terrorism and divergence of thought. As well as what follows like: terrorism, intimidating others, murders, bombing facilities, theft thus menacing the safety of nations all over the world [10]. According to Al-Shahri (2011), "intellectual deviation is one of the most significant threats to security and order. It aims at destabilizing the intellectual convictions, fundamentals of faith and moral social and social standards. No doubt that all the intellectual and behavioral deviations are based usually on a deviated ideology. Due to the fact that, intellectual security is the way to keep the nation safety and stability, it is important to use perfectly social media to be a tool that achieves both stability and security of societies" [11].

The objective of this study is to identify unhealthy behaviors among university students, and their link to the use of social media. It also aims to identify whether digital volunteering can help mitigate unhealthy behavior.

Methodology:

In order to gather data for the study, an anonymous structured questionnaire was given to both students and staff of Princess Nourah bint Abdulrahman University, Riyadh, Saudi Arabia. 220 validly filled questionnaires were returned. The respondents were all females within the age range of 18 and above.

The survey design included questions about socio-demographic characteristics, Types of violating behaviors committed by female students at the university, relationship between the use of social networks and unhealthy behaviors, Reasons behind the wrong behaviors committed by students and Powers used to deal with a student with unhealthy behavior.

The data gathered was subjected to Statistical Package for Social Science (SPSS) 20. Descriptive statistics were used to report the frequencies and percentages for definite variables. Missing data were omitted on a basis analysis-by-analysis and valid percentages were reported. The data was also subjected to correlation analysis to determine the relationship between factors that instigate unhealthy behavior (first axis), detection of unhealthy behavior and awareness of its harms (second axis) and the methods of dealing with the student with unhealthy behaviors (third axis).

Results:

The results from the analysis on the data collected through structured questionnaires are categorically and explicitly represented in the tables and charts below accompanied with a discussion on findings discovered in the study.

Table 1(a) gives the socio-demographic characteristics of the respondents in this research. Most of the respondents (36.4%) were within the ages of 35 and 39 years.

Table 1(a): Social Demographic Characteristics of the Respondents

	Frequency	Percentage
Age		
Less than 25 yrs	30	13.6
25 - 29 yrs	20	9.1

30 - 34 yrs	50	22.7
35 - 39 yrs	80	36.4
Above 40 yrs	40	18.2
Total	220	100.0
Education Level		
Diploma	50	22.7
Bachelor	110	50.0
Master and above	60	27.3
Total	220	100.0
University Specialization		
Law	20	9.1
Public relations	10	4.5
A social service	90	40.9
Industry dental technology	10	4.5
Bachelor of Psychology	10	4.5
Social work	20	9.1
Computer	20	9.1
Business Administration	20	9.1
Educational	10	4.5
Total	210	95.5
Missing System	10	4.5
Total	220	100.0

Table 1 (b) shows that most of the respondents 70 (31.8%) were social workers, followed by social supervisors and security controllers 30 (13.6%) each. The table also shows that most of the respondents have between 1 and 9 years of experience in their respective professions.

Table 1(b): Professionalities of the Respondents

	Frequency	Percentage
Name of Profession		
Social worker	70	31.8
Technical laboratory	10	4.5
Psychologist	10	4.5
social supervisor	30	13.6
a social researcher	10	4.5
Scientific Researcher Assistant	10	4.5
Security surveillance	20	9.1
Security control	30	13.6
Total	190	86.4
Missing System	30	13.6
Total	220	100.0
Number of years of experience		
Less than 5yrs	70	31.8
5 - 9 yrs	70	31.8
10 - 14 yrs	30	13.6
15 yrs and Above	50	22.7
Total	220	100.0

From Table 2 below, Smoking, sexual abnormalities, bullying, verbal abuse were listed by the respondents as common types of unhealthy behaviors among students; with smoking being the commonest single type of unhealthy behavior listed by the respondents 40 (18.2%).

Table 2: Types of violating behaviors committed by female students at the university

	Frequency	Percent
Smoking	40	18.2
Bullying	20	9.1
Prostitution	20	9.1
Smoking, sexual abnormalities, bullying, verbal abuse	50	22.7

An attack on others or on the property, bullying, insults and verbal abuse and vulgar words	40	18.2
Indecent Dressing	10	4.5
Suicide attempt	10	4.5
Smoking, drug abuse and promotion (taboo-doping), sexual abnormalities, verbal Abuse	30	13.6
Total	220	100.0

As obtained from Table 3 below, all the respondents agreed that there is a relationship between the use of social media and the exhibition of unhealthy behavior by students.

Table 3: Is there a relationship between the use of social networks and unhealthy behaviors?

	Frequency	Percent
Yes	170	77.3
Valid To some extent	50	22.7
Total	220	100.0

As shown in Figure 1, the most common sites used by students who suffer from wrong behavior was recreational sites (40.9%), this is followed pornographic sites (22.7%); others utilize both recreation and pornographic sites (22.7%). Recreation, educational and cultural sites combined are the less likely used sites by students suffering from wrong behavior.

Figure 1: Common sites used by students who suffer from wrong behavior

Table 4 presents reasons while students engage in unhealthy behaviors. 100 (45.5%) of the respondents listed search for pleasure/satisfaction of instinct as the prevalent reason behind unhealthy behaviors. Other reasons listed by the respondents were 'to get rich and Escape from the problems and family disputes/Compensation for failure 60 (27.3%) each.

Table 4: Reasons behind the wrong behaviors committed by students

	Frequency	Percent
Search for Pleasure/Satisfaction of instinct	100	45.5
Escape from the problems and family disputes/Compensation for failure	60	27.3
To get rich	60	27.3
Total	220	100.0

From Table 5 below, majority of the respondents 60 (27%) listed awareness and guidance as the power mostly used to deal with student with unhealthy behaviors, followed by disciplinary measures, therapeutics, warnings 20 (9.1%) each. While behavioral modification 10 (4.5%) was presented as the least used power. 70 (31.8%) of the respondents were not aware of powers used to deal with students with unhealthy behaviors.

Table 5: Powers used to deal with a student with unhealthy behavior

	Frequency	Percent
Awareness and Guidance	60	27.3
Behavior Modification	10	4.5
Don't Know	70	31.8
Disciplinary Measures	20	9.1
Therapeutics	20	9.1
Warnings	20	9.1
Guidance and Discipline	20	9.1
Total	220	100.0

Table 6: Correlation between the First, Second and Third axis

		Correlations		
		FIRST_AXIS	SECOND_AXIS	THIRD_AXIS
FIRST_AXIS	Pearson Correlation	1	0.365	0.899**
	Sig. (2-tailed)		0.094	0.000
	N	220	220	220
SECOND_AXIS	Pearson Correlation	0.365	1	0.375
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.094		0.086
	N	22	22	22
THIRD_AXIS	Pearson Correlation	0.899**	0.375	1
	Sig. (2-tailed)	0.000	0.086	
	N	220	220	220

** Correlation is significant at the 0.01 level (2-tailed).

The first axis: factors that instigate unhealthy behavior; **The second axis:** detection of unhealthy behavior and awareness of its harms; **third axis:** the methods of dealing with the student.

From Table 6, the correlation between the first and second axis is 0.365 indicating a weak relationship between factors that instigate unhealthy behavior and the detection of unhealthy behavior (and awareness of its harms). The Sig. (2 tailed) is 0.094 indicating that there is a statistically significant correlation between the two variables.

The first and third axes are strongly correlated as the Pearson correlation value is 0.899 thus there is a correlation between factors that instigate unhealthy behavior and the methods of dealing with the student. As observed from the table, it is a positive correlation thus an increase in the value of the first variable (the first axis: factors that instigate unhealthy behavior) will result to increase the value of the other variable (third axis: the methods of dealing with the student). The Sig. (2 tailed) is less than 0.05 indicating that there is no statistically significant correlation between the two variables (first and second axis).

There is a weak relationship between the second and third axis between factors that instigate unhealthy behavior and the detection of unhealthy behavior (and awareness of its harms). The Sig. (2 tailed) is 0.086 indicating that there is a statistically significant correlation between the two variables.

Discussion

This study was of clearly stated objectives. The characteristics of the respondent's /university students/personnel were well portrayed, randomized sampling was also utilized, the studied topic is considered new in the fields of volunteering work.

Volunteering activities span across various age groups, levels of education, and professions. The youths and young adults are key players volunteering activities. This may be as a result of altruism [12], others include taking volunteering as a national duty, for development of skills and leadership abilities. As revealed by the study, while smoking, sexual abnormalities, bullying and verbal abuse are violating behaviors committed by female students at the university, smoking alone constituted the commonest of them all. In this study, 18.2% of respondents reported smoking as the most violating behavior committed by female students at the university which is consistent with a number of studies such as Felimban (1993) who reported a prevalence of 8.3% [13] and Merdad, Al-Zahrani& Farsi (2007) who reported 11%. Smokers (tobacco users) were much more likely to be in contact with someone (whether online or offline) who smokes [14]. Awareness of the dangers and consequences of smoking and other unhealthy behavior will help curtail smoking among university students.

This awareness should be made before a student starts smoking [15]. Unhealthy behavior which is eventually risky to the victims is habitually established during youth and pull out to adulthood (Refaat, 2004) and thus need to be confronted with all possible measures [16].

According to the United Nations Volunteer program, “technological developments are opening up spaces for people to volunteer in ways that have no parallel in history” [17]. Digital or electronic volunteering “has eliminated the need for volunteerism to be tied to definite times and locations. Thus, it greatly increases the freedom and flexibility of volunteer engagement and complements the outreach and impact of volunteers serving in situ” [17]. The outburst in mobile technology and social media in particular has decreased the information and communication hurdles to contributing in disaster rejoinder and recuperation [18]. Therefore, “it has driven a growth in digitally-enabled emergent volunteering following disasters that occur both online and on-site, or, as is frequently the case, in interaction” [19, 20]. Meier (2012); Zooket *al.* (2010) stated that “The phenomenon of digital disaster volunteering in particular has garnered significant research attention since the massive response of digital volunteers to the 2010 Haiti earthquake”. [21, 22]. “This was a turning point event that paved way for digital humanitarianism that is really international in reach” [18]. Significantly, digital volunteers have been found more successful than conventional government organizations at organizing, assembling, managing and publicizing the “data deluge” that is prompted by disasters in the digital age in close to simultaneous to increase conditional knowledge [23, 24, 25, 26, 27, 28]. According to Haworth and Bruce (2015), “a key strength of digital volunteering arises from the huge capacity of the internet to facilitate crowd-sourcing, mostly for volunteered geographic information (VGI)”. VGI “involves the sharing and mapping of spatial data through voluntary information gathered by the general public” [29], and it is especially influential for disaster circumstances. This is progressively more recognized by well-known players. Conspicuously, the Information Services Section (ISS) of the United Nations Office for the Coordination of Humanitarian Affairs (OCHA) started a digital volunteering network—The Standby Taskforce—to create live, crowd-sourced crisis maps for the 2011 Libyan revolution that was afterwards used by humanitarian organizations to manage their relieve activities [21].

Unhealthy behavior among adolescents in the school setting has been linked to obesity, low academic accomplishment, more numerous health complaints, life skills, poor self-reported health status longer time spent watching TV, regular smoking, poor emotional well-being and unhealthy eating habits and drunkenness, [30, 31, 32, 33].

Some investigations have revealed that physical inactivity and smoking are linked with the magnitude of the associates, and that physical inactivity alcohol use and smoking, are associated with the regularity of associates connection [34, 35]. A variety of researchers have established that health disparities connected to associates and academic settings occur both in unhealthy behaviors, like alcohol consumption and smoking, and in different positive health behaviors [36]. Furthermore, researches on socio-economic status have established that variations among youths are explained better by peer group and the school environment rather than by SES [33].

Conclusions and Recommendations

The results show that unhealthy behaviors exist among university students and these unhealthy behaviors are strongly linked to the use of social media. The study also reveals that digital volunteering can help to mitigate unhealthy behaviors and its effect among university students. The following recommendations were made based on these findings:

Efforts should be geared towards intensifying volunteer work in terms of creation of awareness. There should be budgets and incentives for the team and those in charge of volunteer groups. There should be more volunteering programs and initiatives to interact with external centers related to behavior modification. More opportunities should be provided for students to participate in volunteering programs. Students who participate in volunteer programs should be honored by awarding them certificate of appreciation to motivate them and inspire others to volunteer. There should be establishment of programs and campaigns designed to modify the behavior of students. There should be training programs to educate students on the importance and benefits of volunteering.

Abbreviations

Not applicable.

Declarations

Ethics approval and consent to participate

Ethics approval was obtained for this study from the International Review Board (IRB) in Princess Nourah bint Abdulrahman University.

Consent for publication

Not applicable.

Availability of data and materials

Any raw data or materials used in the preparation of this manuscript are available upon reasonable request to Dr. Samar Alshawwa (samarzuhair@yahoo.com)

Competing of interests

The authors declare that they have no competing interests.

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Authors' contribution

All authors were responsible for the initiation, conceptualization and leadership of the guideline development process. AA and SA were responsible for the respondent's survey. RA and SA were responsible for the data statistical analysis and interpretation of results. AA was the primary author of the manuscript. All coauthors were responsible for writing, reviewing, and revising the manuscript for important intellectual content. All authors read and approved the final manuscript, participated in the study and questionnaire design, data analysis, drafted the manuscript, and approved it before submission.

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